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SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSIONS OF SAND MINING IN BADULU OYA, SRI LANKA: A QUALITATIVE AND GIS-BASED STUDY

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Sand mining is a crucial livelihood activity in rural Sri Lanka, especially in the Badulu Oya area, providing essential income for local communities. However, unregulated mining has led to significant environmental harm and institutional challenges. This study aims to examine the socioeconomic, financial, and environmental aspects of sand mining using a qualitative approach complemented by GIS-based land use and land cover (LULC) analysis from 2016 to 2024. The research reveals that while sand mining remains a lucrative but unstable source of income—affected by seasonal changes, delays in licensing, and scarce alternative jobs—workers also face health risks from polluted water. Gender-specific labor roles and bureaucratic obstacles limit fair participation. Financially, despite high returns compared to other rural options, increasing costs and regulatory issues reduce profitability. Environmentally, sand mining has intensified riverbank erosion, reduced biodiversity, and caused land degradation. Governance is fragmented, with weak enforcement, limited public involvement, and insufficient data-based resource management. Based on stakeholder input and environmental change analysis, the study proposes a six-point strategy for sustainable sand mining in rural settings. It further reframes sand mining as a rural governance issue, connecting informal labor, environmental vulnerability, and institutional gaps. These findings offer valuable methodological and conceptual insights relevant to other regions. The study highlights the urgent need for integrated rural governance approaches that balance environmental protection with socioeconomic stability.

Keywords: Sand mining, Rural livelihoods, Environmental degradation, Governance